

D3.3 Final version of integrated and tested DIANA service platform

**WP3 DIANA service platform design and
development**

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Introduction

DIANA service platform was created in order to empower water managers and authorities in handling the challenging issue of water management in agriculture. In order to achieve that DIANA services were designed to assist them both in monitoring, as well as planning the respective activities through three core services: i) non-authorized illegal water abstractions; ii) drought monitoring; and iii) monitoring of the water framework directive.

The foundation for the final version of DIANA platform was set in the first year of the project through a number of actions. One of those was the elicitation of the user requirements through a co-creation process, during which all parties became stakeholders of the final product. The output of the process is described in detail in the respective deliverables (*D1.2 Report on co-creation outcomes: DIANA services and pilot use cases* and *D1.3 Specifications of DIANA services*). User requirements were subsequently turned into technical requirements and along with the system architecture, design and integration, they became the cornerstone for the first version of DIANA platform (*D3.1 Overall architecture, system design and integration framework specification*). Another parameter that came into place in order for the first version of the service platform to be realized was the earth observation methodology that would be used for DIANA services (*D2.1 EO Methodology for DIANA services*).

Based upon those building blocks, during the second year of the project, the first version of DIANA platform was developed. In that initial version the main focus was on developing the various components and interfaces to be used by the different pilots for the validation of DIANA services. Apart from the development, a thorough testing process was also in place to ensure minimum impact on the activities of the pilots and prompt resolving of issues that came up. A detailed description of the output of that action is included in the respective deliverable (*D3.2: 1st version of integrated and tested DIANA service platform*).

The focus during the last year of the project was shifted in improving DIANA platform and providing in the end of the project a feature complete platform, ready for commercial uptake. More specifically, having incorporated DIANA services in their daily workflow, pilot users were able to evaluate the first version of the platform and provide valuable input on improvements that would upgrade the final product. In the following chapters the final version of DIANA platform, the development process that was followed, the feedback that was received by the users and finally the improvements that took place, are going to be described in detail.

1. Final DIANA service platform

DIANA service platform provides a unified services access, management, and operation environment for water managers and authorities. The service platform was chosen as a means to bridge the different technologies and provide a common structure for service delivery. As a result, the platform connects maps, data, and people in ways that help them make more informed and better decisions. DIANA makes it easy for the various actors in a water authority to create, use and share maps and data, depending on their role.

The roles of DIANA platform were identified early on, in D3.1 Overall architecture, system design and integration framework specification:

- the Administrator (A)
- the Water Managers (WM) and
- the Inspectors (I).

Based on that identification, users can access different parts of the platform and execute different actions. For example only Administrators can provide user access and approve or reject a new registration request in the system. Furthermore, super administrator can provide or reject access over specific geospatial areas, even within the same country and region. There is also the possibility for combined access to different areas and different stakeholders of DIANA platform.

For the provision of the services, a lot of work was done during the first two years and on the foundations that were laid down and more information can be found in “D3.1 Overall architecture, system design and integration framework specification” and “D3.2. 1st version of integrated and tested DIANA service platform”. In the last year of DIANA project, a number of improvements were carried out in regards to the platform to ensure the best outcome. Those concerned both the backend system, as well as the front end. In the first instance the aim was to improve the accuracy of the results, while in the second the aim was for the platform to become more user-friendly to simplify the work of the end users and ensure easier adoption of the product.

Those improvements did not influence the main logic that the DIANA platform was designed upon, since they were fully compliant to the product baseline, as it was set in the user requirements phase. Hence, DIANA platform is based on a three layer logic that consists:

- the spatial and data layer;
- the application layer; and
- the frontend layer.

The components included in those layers, in brief, are the following:

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- DIANA API;
- GIS dashboard;
- Web application;
- Mobile application; and
- Mobile application.

Figure 1- DIANA architecture

Each of the components that were developed during the second year of the project, served a specific purpose such as: the modularity of the system, meaning that at any time parts of the system can be changed or replaced without affecting the overall system; the robustness of the system, meaning that any necessary computational actions can be performed by the system at any time without any dependencies from other parameters; the visibility and availability of all key information, meaning that all the necessary information for operations and decision making are of high importance; accessibility of the system, meaning that the system needs to be available at any time, through various means to accommodate end users. More details can be found in the following chapters.

2. Development processes evaluation

For the development of DIANA platform the iterative¹ development approach was chosen as also indicated in D3.1. Overall architecture, system design and integration framework specification. The basic idea underlying the iterative development methodology was that a bigger project can be broken down into smaller parts. Hence, those parts had better defined scope and duration. Furthermore, the iterative approach allowed for user requirements not to be fully defined from early on the project. Rather the development started with the requirements to the functional part and were later on expanded.

Furthermore, the iterative process allowed for new versions of the product, which were released in different times throughout the project. Every iteration included the development of a separate component of the system, which was then added to the ones that were developed earlier on. Thus, unlike the waterfall process the iterative allowed for the addition of features one-by-one, providing a working product by the end of one of the first iterations and increased the overall functionality of the system step by step.

The reason why the iterative methodology was chosen over other ones was twofold: i) the iterative process allows for development to start without all requirements being defined. This is considered as an advantage in development, since it is more often than not that users may change some of the requirements, as the project progresses. In other words the iterative process allowed in the case of DIANA for a flexibility to changes, for which the technical team was also more prepared, since they could incorporate them in one of the upcoming iterations; ii) the technical team also had the flexibility to deliver a working prototype, while keep building on that and adding more components and features. Although the first iterations may not have included the full final product, they delivered a working prototype to the end users. That allowed for the final product to be better tailored to their needs.

In the case of DIANA platform the iterative approach was chosen after careful consideration and became a valuable tool for the technical team. Along with the involvement of stakeholders from

¹ <https://www.techopedia.com/definition/26100/iterative-development>

early on the project, the use of the iterative approach ensured that a complex and sophisticated platform was developed and aligned with the business requirements. More specifically the following parameters helped the technical team affectively deliver the service platform:

1. The collaboration with business stakeholders that helped the technical team to envision their needs. Engaging stakeholders early in the planning process helped in identifying the business value a component can provide for the overall system, the balance value against risk, and as a resulted set the development priorities. Although significant amount of work held on those parts during the first few months of the project and then before each iteration we would revisit and revise the user requirements mainly and when needed also the rest of the parts.
2. The use of the iteration process. The technical team was able to deliver the first working prototype early in the project, delivering thus quickly value and on the long term building toward a successful implementation. By focusing on incremental enhancements that, the technical team tried to avoid spending development time on functionality that adds unnecessary complexity. As a result, even from the first iteration a large part of the functionality was included, and as the project progressed and users provided their feedback, improvements and changes were realized.
3. Finally, the iteration process helped in continuing iterating the platform, since more useful feedback was provided by the final users and stakeholders. Apart from using the iterations as a tool to co-create the platform and the early involvement of the users, the services and overall functionality of the platform were also co-validated. That allowed for more insights and improvements to take place, adding more business value to the final product.

All in all the development process that was selected for DIANA platform was one that would be suitable for delivering added value to the final product. It was a process that would ensure the maximum satisfaction of the final users and their business needs and that would avoid depreciating value instead.

3. DIANA integration in the user workflow

3.1. The added value of DIANA platform

Water managers and authorities have to do some repetitive manual tasks that take a lot of time, effort, and focus; decrease overall productivity; and increase risk. The impacts of those tasks are compounded as the number of tasks grows, but they can be mitigated and that can happen through automation.

Automation allows technology to create and maintain infrastructure and programmatically execute the steps of a well-defined workflow, while at the same time limiting human interaction. More specifically such tools that automate common tasks such as data management, analysis, map production and deployment of operations improve:

1. **Efficiency:** information is most useful to the decision making process when it is delivered in a timely manner. Because automating tasks and resource allocation improves efficiency, work can be completed faster and new information can be delivered to stakeholders sooner. This boost in efficiency allows for returning greater value to the business.
2. **Consistency:** when tasks are executed manually, errors are more common and outcomes can be inconsistent, unreliable, and costly. Once developed and properly tested, automated processes are highly dependable and can be replicated with identical and predictable results. Automated processes save time, minimize duplicated efforts, and increase confidence in business operations.
3. **Productivity:** automation can improve deployment, administration, and end-user workflows. By using automation to execute tasks, users are able to complete them faster, and thus they can increase overall productivity. This encourages them to apply the same systems and/or methods to additional business initiatives, such as strategic projects, research and development efforts, and other high-value projects that might otherwise go unfulfilled. With automation, administrative workflows and process data are done more efficiently, consistently, and routinely. Hence this improves operational efficiency and the effectiveness and timeliness of decision-making, freeing resources for other tasks and boosting the value of any organization.

One of those tools that were created for water authorities and managers and applies the power of geography to improve workflows throughout an organization, is DIANA. The integrated service platform automates a lot of the common tasks of water managers and supports them in their operations. Furthermore, DIANA platform organizes users and connects them with the appropriate content and capabilities based on their role and privileges within the platform.

Overall, DIANA delivers capabilities that support key requirements, goals, and initiatives that help water authorities improve their business outcomes. By working along with the stakeholders from the beginning of the project, the team managed to define the capabilities that must be delivered, and align DIANA with real business needs.

3.2. Integration in the user workflow

An important aspect of the project was the integration of the services into the user workflow. It should be noted that irrigation water management happens in a complex web of institutional settings and private initiatives, which differ greatly from one country or region to another. As a result in the current document we are going to showcase a high level example of the integration into the user flow, without going deep into the particularities of each different country and/or area.

In general, as indicated in D1.2, a Water Users Association (WUA) is in charge of managing the water resources of an irrigation network or of an aquifer. Before the beginning of the irrigation season, the WUA develops an exploitation plan based on the water resources allocation they receive from the respective authority e.g. the river-basin authority. That exploitation plan, defines the water that can be used by a specific area based on its' specific characteristics (i.e. crops).

As soon as that plan is in place the Administrator of that area can sign into DIANA platform and assign Water Managers (WMs) and Inspectors for the upcoming season.

The screenshot shows the 'My Profile' form in the DIANA platform. The form is titled 'My Profile' and is located under the 'Users' menu. It contains the following fields:

- Name:** A text input field with the placeholder 'Enter name' and a note 'Please enter a name'.
- Last Name:** A text input field with the placeholder 'Enter last name' and a note 'Please enter a last name'.
- Email Address:** A text input field with the placeholder 'Enter email' and a note 'We'll never share the email with anyone else'.
- Organization:** A dropdown menu with the placeholder 'Choose Organization'.
- Department:** A dropdown menu with the placeholder 'Choose Department'.
- Role:** A dropdown menu with the placeholder 'Choose Role'.
- Language:** A dropdown menu with the placeholder 'Choose language'.

At the bottom of the form, there is a note: 'An automatically generated password will be sent to the user after email confirmation.'

Figure 2 - Administrator profile for assigning roles

As soon as WMs are assigned, are responsible for monitoring the irrigation water consumption over the season (weekly or monthly), and reassure that irrigation water is applied in compliance with the exploitation plan, over their area of responsibility. Having at their disposal the plan and the farmers' declarations, WMs are able to sign in to DIANA platform and start their activities.

Initially, WMs are able to check the crop classification based on DIANA platform and the irrigation rights that they have available. This provides them with an overview of the entire area under their responsibility. Knowing the crop type WMs are able to understand various parameters, such as the expected crop evapotranspiration and/or the expected gross crop water requirements.

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Figure 3 - Crop classification map

As soon as they are familiarized with the crop classification map in the platform, WMs start monitoring Crop Evapotranspiration and Irrigation Requirements.

Figure 4 - Monthly monitoring of evapotranspiration

DIANA provides WMs with the seasonally estimated crop ET, and enables them to view the monthly crop water requirements. To strategically plan ahead, WMs can take into consideration

the seasonal drought forecast. The coupled monthly water requirements and irrigation rights provide a first indicator of possible illegal abstractions.

Figure 5 - Gross Irrigation Water Requirements

Water requirements, along with the crop classification map and the drought tool, comprise another indicator for the WMs. With DIANA platform a large or a small scale monitoring can be performed based on the area of interest. This is valuable information for a manager to decide on allocation of resources for on-site inspections for over abstractions. In the case of illegal abstractions, WMs can combine the information from the map layers, to identify areas or parcels of possible illegal actions in advance.

Nevertheless, bi-weekly or monthly signing in to the platform, allows for WMs to closely monitor the progression of the situation for the overall area and for specific parcels as well. After the first few months from the beginning of the irrigation season and having good indicators at their disposal, WMs can assign Inspectors to targeted areas (and not random checks). Inspectors then can go and perform in-field evaluations. They have at their disposal all the necessary information, such as the declaration of the farmer and the water volumes that will accommodate their inspection process. Using DIANA mobile Inspectors send their feedback back to the WMs along with important evidence, since the DIANA mobile app allows them to upload photos of the field or a hydrometer. That enables WMs to also compare the satellite images with the on-site information, making a strong case against “offenders”, which allows for any further actions.

4. Platform changes and improvements

As mentioned in the previous parts, although the initial version of the platform was created quite early in the project, nevertheless in the following versions adjustments and improvements were made based on the co-creation process and the feedback that was received from the users. Within that framework in the following parts we are showcasing the various changes that took place in the last year of the project.

4.1. Water abstractions

One of the most important additions that were made during the last year was that of the addition of two more calculation parameters for the provided statistics. Although initially the basis for the calculation of the statistics were the gross irrigation requirements, net irrigation requirements and evapotranspiration were added as the basis for running the calculations for the statistics that are provided in the platform.

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Another improvement that was made to the water abstractions service was the addition of a feature that allows water managers to see the statistics for a specific area. Either by uploading a pre-defined area or by drawing an area of interest, water managers are able to “investigate” and focus on a specific area. As soon as the area is defined the statistics provided in the platform are adjusted.

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Another addition was the capability of Water Managers to “Print” the statistics and map of the area that they are navigating. As a result users can share or save the results for the whole area, or a specific area of interest. Another enhancement on the map control that focuses on making the navigation easier, is the addition of coordinates on the bottom of the map. When the user navigates in the map the coordinates are indicating the exact navigation location. That way, users can find or navigate in a specific area of interest easily.

4.2. Drought forecast and monitoring

Apart from the improvements that took place for the water abstractions service, some enhancements were also made for the drought forecasting and monitoring tool. Those concerned mainly the addition of layers of data which the Water Managers can use.

4.3. User interface

Improvements were also made to the user interface with the objective of improving the user experience. That includes the practical, experiential, affective meaningful and valuable aspects of the human-application interaction, including system aspects as utility, ease of use and efficiency. More attention was paid to details such as colors, texts and values to ensure a complete and comprehensive output for the final user.

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4.4. Operational functionality

One of the most important features that was added during the last year of the project was the platform being put into operational use, which was only possible after all functionalities and components were in place, tested and evaluated. The operational use translates into the full independency of users from the need for constant technical support. Water authorities can manage their data at any time. They can choose the data to FTP and upload in the database or deduct from the platform and as soon as they log in they are able to see their updated statistics and respective map layers. Detailed guidelines were issued from the technical team that fully describe the process that need to be followed in order for the users to be able to visualize their data. The guidelines can be found below:

- *Projection of all georeferenced files must be WGS 84 (EPSG:4326)*
- *Layers (i.e irrigated areas) must have the same columns per country because they will be inserted on the same PostGIS table*

Maps of Irrigated Areas

/upload/outputs/maps_of_irrigated_areas/[COUNTRY]/[REGION]/[YEAR]

<i>irrigated_2017.shp</i>	<i>Shape Irrigated Field DN with value 1</i>
<i>non-irrigated_2017.shp</i>	<i>Shape Non-Irrigated Field DN with value 0</i>
<i>cropClassification_2017.tif</i>	<i>Geotiff Check Crop Classification IDs section below</i>
<i>water_rights_2017.shp</i>	<i>Shape</i>

Crop Water Requirements

Monthly

/upload/outputs/maps_of_irrigated_water_reqs/COUNTRY]/[REGION]/etc/[YEAR]

<i>etc_20180101.tif</i>	<i>Geotiff</i>
<i>etc_20180201.tif</i>	<i>Geotiff</i>
<i>etc_20180301.tif</i>	<i>Geotiff</i>

Annual

/upload/outputs/maps_of_irrigated_water_reqs/COUNTRY]/[REGION]/etc/[YEAR]/annual/

<i>etc_2018.tif</i>	<i>Geotiff</i>
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Net Irrigation Water Requirements

Monthly

/upload/outputs/maps_of_irrigated_water_reqs/COUNTRY]/[REGION]/niwr/[YEAR]

<i>niwr_20180101.tif</i>	<i>Geotiff</i>
<i>niwr_20180201.tif</i>	<i>Geotiff</i>
<i>niwr_20180301.tif</i>	<i>Geotiff</i>

Annual

/upload/outputs/maps_of_irrigated_water_reqs/[COUNTRY]/[REGION]/niwr/[YEAR]/annual/

<i>niwr_2018.tif</i>	<i>Geotiff</i>
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Gross Irrigation Water Requirements

Monthly

/upload/outputs/maps_of_irrigated_water_reqs/COUNTRY]/[REGION]/giwr/[YEAR]

<i>giwr_20180101.tif</i>	<i>Geotiff</i>
<i>giwr_20180201.tif</i>	<i>Geotiff</i>
<i>giwr_20180301.tif</i>	<i>Geotiff</i>

Annual

/upload/outputs/maps_of_irrigated_water_reqs/COUNTRY]/[REGION]/giwr/[YEAR]/annual/

<i>giwr_2018.tif</i>	<i>Geotiff</i>
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Crop Classification IDS

Mancha

- 1 = Spring*
- 2 = Summer*
- 3 = Spring-Summer*
- 4 = Vineyard*
- 5 = Olive Trees*
- 7 = Orchards*
- 8 = Nut Trees*

Bajo Jalon

- 1 = Spring*
- 2 = Summer*
- 3 = Spring-Summer*
- 4 = Vineyard*
- 5 = Olive Trees*
- 7 = Orchards*
- 8 = Nut Trees*
- 9 = Greenhouse*

10 = Autumn-Winter

Tierra del Vino

1 = Spring

2 = Summer

3 = Spring-Summer

4 = Vineyard

7 = Orchards

8 = Nut Trees

9 = Greenhouse

10 = Autumn-Winter

Bembezar

11 = Tomato

12 = Sugarbeet

13 = Cotton

14 = Corn

15 = Sunflower

16 = Alfalfa

17 = Citrus

18 = Bare soil

Sannio Alifano

1 = Herbaceous

2 = Tree

Banat

101 = COMMON AUTUMN WHEAT

102 = HARD AUTUMN WHEAT

108 = MAIZE

110 = SORGHUM

201 = SUNFLOWER

202 = AUTUMN RAPESEED

451 = FODDER PLANTS

970 = NOT CULTIVATED LAND

2037 = SOYBEANS

3017 = SUGAR BEET

9747 = ALFALFA

5. Conclusions

In conclusion the final version of DIANA service platform is a ready for the market product that could be adopted by current and other potential users. As mentioned in the beginning of the document the platform is feature complete and finalized as far as the technical aspect is concerned. We aspire thus that with the experience of the SMEs of DIANA consortium the service platform will become a necessity for all interested parties and will support them in making the difference with a valuable resource: water!

